

Rituals Related to the Birth of a Child in the Surkhandarya Oasis

Tursunov Nurullo Narzullaevich

Termez University of Economics and Service, Associate Professor of the Department of Social and Humanities, doctor of historical sciences (DSc), Termez (Uzbekistan)

Abstract: *This article talks about the meaning and analysis of weddings in the national rituals of the Uzbeks using the example of the Surkhan oasis. At the same time, it is analyzed that the traditions associated with wedding ceremonies, characteristic of the oasis, preserved from ancient times and not losing their meaning to this day, are based on certain rules and norms, depending on the ethnolocal family.*

The article also reflects that among the inhabitants of the oasis, family customs and rituals at the end of the 19th - beginning of the 20th century were more clearly manifested in the lifestyle of the sedentary population compared to the semi-sedentary one.

Key words: *country, oasis, territory, clan, tribe, family, nation, value, ritual, ethnography, wedding, custom, tradition, custom, national consciousness, image, faith.*

During the years of Uzbekistan's independence, researchers have conducted significant scientific research on the study of national customs, traditions, and values, leading to significant results. In the process of studying the ethnography of the Surkhan Oasis, which is considered the southern region of our country, due to the scientific study of sources related to wedding ceremonies, which are considered one of the oldest traditions of our people, special attention is paid to instilling our national values in the minds of the younger generation, as well as to peacefully and calmly holding weddings according to national traditions, preventing waste based on the organization of low costs, and providing comprehensive material and moral support to young families.

Having studied the organization of weddings characteristic of the way of life of our people and their historical foundations, the following analyses were noted. As we know, family and domestic rituals arose as a result of the need for social life and arose on the basis of human intellect, spiritual, moral, and legal needs. In this regard, these rituals are the product of a long historical development. Because "In the East, family has long been considered a sacred homeland." If the family is healthy and strong, peace and tranquility will be achieved in the mahalla. Therefore, peace and stability will prevail in the state only when the neighborhood is strong." [1] As President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Effective struggle against actions that negatively affect the consciousness of the population, especially our youth, aimed at their ideological dependence, as well as the development of specific annual programs of measures to raise a strong-willed, selfless, patriotic and independent generation, implementation of measures aimed at eliminating vices such as disregard for family values and irresponsible attitude towards the upbringing of youth." Even today, the family rituals of the oasis's inhabitants have much in common with the family rituals of the people living in other regions of Uzbekistan, but they are distinguished by the richness of customs and traditions, as well as the preservation of specific ethnic and local features of the tradition of rituals. It is well known from history that customs and rituals are a social phenomenon inextricably linked to the domestic life of the family and have been developed since the early stages of societal

development.[3] These customs and rituals, in connection with their ancient past, are rooted in the traditions of societal development, based on religious beliefs.

In the family rituals and customs of local peoples such as Uzbeks, Tajiks, Turkmens, and Arabs of the Surkhan Oasis, we can observe that the traditional customs and rituals characteristic of such ancient times are well preserved to this day.[4]

There are a number of customs and rituals associated with traditional weddings in the oasis, such as a childbirth wedding, a cradle wedding, a hair wedding, a circumcision wedding, a wedding, a court wedding, a mustache wedding, a prophet's age wedding.[5]

Weddings and ceremonies related to childhood were held in the family in various forms, with specific customs and traditions. One of the family rituals of the residents of the Surkhandarya oasis is the birth of a child.[6] The Uzbek people have always been children. For this reason, folk sayings such as "Ten is a place, forty is a different thing," "A house with children is a market, a house without children is a cemetery," "Be a dog, be a bird, be many" were woven among the people. Because the Uzbek people considered having many children to be a guarantee of family stability. It was firmly believed that the more children there are in the family, the stronger the family will be. Family size was necessary for economic activity. The higher the number of livestock breeders in semi-settled families, the more livestock products were grown. The semi-nomadic population also engaged in dryland farming alongside animal husbandry. Therefore, farming farms also needed to have many children.[7] The birth of a child in a family was considered a great joy.

In the Surkhan oasis, when a child is born, a "Birthday" or "Aqiqa" ceremony is held. Aqiqa is one of the rituals performed when a child is born.[8] The "aqiqa" ceremony, performed at the birth of a child in the oasis, was also unique. Aqiqa is one of the rituals performed when a Muslim gives birth to a child. The Aqiqa wedding was celebrated by slaughtering two sheep if they had a son and one sheep if they had a daughter, depending on the oasis's capabilities.[9] After 9, 10, or 11 days after the birth of the baby, if it was a boy, it was stained in the cradle, and after 21 days, mainly 40 days, that is, after the chilla, a cradle wedding was held. A cradle wedding was held seven days later, saying that if the eldest child was a girl, there would be seven pink administrators of this family. It is one of the important celebrations held after a child is born.[10] The cradle wedding had its own characteristics, which also depended on the family's economic strength. Each family, based on its economic capabilities, slaughtered sheep and goats, calling neighbors, relatives, and friends.

An old man, in some cases a village mullah, prays to the child's ear and gives him his name. The baby was bathed mainly when he was three days old, and if a boy was bathed, meat and coins were added to the salt water to make it rich. A ring was thrown into the water so that the girl would be happy.

The custom of "chilla quvdi" was performed when the child was born, that is, on the fortyth day of the child's birth. The baby's mother bakes a wheat casserole and carries the baby to the house of her closest friends. People in this house eat fries. To make the baby's face brighter, he gives him a white robe and the newborn is kissed by the host. At first, it was believed that if he kissed the baby's forehead, he would become a figurehead, if he kissed his chest, he would become a famous wrestler, and if he kissed his hand, he would become a generous rich man.[11]

The leg wedding was held when the child began to walk. This custom was also called "tushov kesdi" in the Baysun, Sherabad, Altynsay, Denau, and Sariasiya districts of the oasis. The child's first independent walk was greeted with great joy in the family. Of course, this depended on the family's economic situation. Parents, close relatives, and friends celebrated this joy in a solemn manner.[12] Special preparations were made for the wedding, and then the wedding day was set. During the wedding, the "toy-toy" is dressed in new clothes and tied with a thin cotton thread ("tušov") that does not interfere with the child's leg movement. While the boy was slowly toying, the thread between his two feet was

cut by an old man with a scissor saying "the downy cut, the downy cut" and was moved in front of the guests. The child was scattered over money, coins, and various kinds of sweets, called "sachala," meaning "hair." Newlyweds and brides gathered the scattered children, hoping that we too would have such children. This ceremony, known as the leg wedding, was also held in one way or another in other regions of the republic.[14]

In conclusion, it can be said that the ceremonies associated with the birth of a child in the Surkhandarya oasis were not only unique, but also had common features with other regions of the republic.

References:

1. Каримов И.А. Оила фаровонлиги-миллат фаровонлиги / Хавфсизлик ва барқарор тараққиёт йўлида. Т. 6. -Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 1998. -400 б.
2. Мирзиёев Ш.М. Янги Ўзбекистон стратегияси. -Тошкент: "O'zbekiston", 2021. -474 б.
3. Аширов А. Ўзбек халқининг қадимий эътиқод ва маросимлари.-Т.: А. Навоий номидаги Ўзбек миллий кутубхонаси нашриёти, 2007.-275 б.
4. Дала ёзувлари. Жарқўрғон, Бойсун, Термиз, Музработ, Шеробод туманлари 2020-2021 йиллар.
5. Турсунов Н.Н. Жанубий Сурхон воҳаси этнографияси. -Тошкент: "Yangi nashr", 2015.-160 б.
6. Хоразмда бу тўй "туғуш тўй" деб аталган. *Қаранг*: Снесарев Г.П. Реликты домусульманских верований и обрядов у узбеков Хорезма.-М., 1969. -336 с; Фирштейн Л.А. О некоторых обычаях и поверьях, связанных с рождением и воспитанием ребенка у узбеков Южного Хорезма // Семья и семейные обряды у народов Средней Азии и Казахстана. -М., 1978. -213 с.
7. Шониёзов К. Ўзбек халқининг шаклланиш жараёни.-Т.: -Шарқ, 2001.-462 б; Каримов И.А. Оила фаровонлиги-миллат фаровонлиги / Хавфсизлик ва барқарор тараққиёт йўлида. Т. 6. -Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 1998.-400 б.
8. Турсунов Н.Н. Жанубий Сурхон воҳаси этнографияси. -Тошкент: "Yangi nashr", 2015.-160 б.
9. *Ақиқа ҳақида қаранг*: Исмоил ал-Бухорий. Ал-жомеъ ас-саҳиҳ. 3-китоб. -Тошкент, 1997.-Б. 509; Бобохонов Ш.З. Исломда ақиқа масаласи // Шарқшунослик.-Тошкент, 1994. №5.-Б.104; Сейка Вазаки. Ўзбек халқи анъанавий турмуш тарзида «ақиқа» маросими // Республика ёш олимларининг илмий тўплами. -Тошкент, 2008. -Б. 91-92.
10. Ташбаева Т.Х., Савуров М.Д. Новое и традиционное в быту сельской семьи узбеков. -Ташкент, 1989.-163 с.
11. Турсунов Н.Н. Жанубий Сурхон воҳаси этнографияси. -Тошкент: "Yangi nashr", 2015.-160 б.
12. Дала ёзувлари. Бойсун, Шеробод, Олтинсой, Денов, Сарийосиё туманлари 2014-2015 йиллар.
13. Сочқи сочиш Ўзбекистоннинг бошқа вилоятларида ҳам бўлган. *Қаранг*: Ташбаева Т.Х., Савуров М.Д. Новое и традиционное в быту сельской семьи узбеков.-Ташкент, 1989.-163 с.
14. *Қаранг*: Гершенович Р.С. О бытовой гигиене узбекского грудного ребенка // Труды САГУ. Серия XII-б. Этнография. Вып. II. –Ташкент, 1928. -С. 11; Троицкая А.Л. Рождение и первые годы жизни ребенка у таджиков долины Зарафшана // СЭ.-М., 1935. -№.6. -С.132.